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M2.6 Workshop to discuss ontology design good practices and evaluate the first recommendations and the roadmap

Work Package	WP2 FAIR Semantics and Semantics for FAIR
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Workshop Objectives

The goal of the Task 2.2 of the FAIRsFAIR project is to co-create both recommendations for making semantic artefacts FAIR, and a set of agreed best practices to follow together with the Semantics community at large. The term "semantic artefact" is being used here as a catchall term covering ontologies, KOS (Knowledge Organization Systems), and any other similar 'tools' which allow researchers and machines to describe, locate, access, and understand (meta)data. This could also include data vocabularies, code, code lists, and standards.

Our goal for this workshop, arranged virtually on 15 October 2020, was to go through the recommendations one by one and discuss feedback and proposed changes in advance of the second iteration (1st Set of FAIR Semantics: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3707985>).

Workshop Organisation

Invitations had been sent via email to experts and the workshop was announced on the fairsfair.eu site (<https://fairsfair.eu/events/recommendations-fair-semantics>). The platforms used were Zoom, Mentimeter, Google Drive and github (<https://github.com/FAIRsFAIR/FAIRSemantics>). When using the Zoom chat or making comments in the collaborative notes the participants were instructed to add the reference of the recommendation to their comments:

- The numbers for the Preliminary Recommendations :#1 - #17 ([Appendix A](#))
- The Best Practice Preliminary -Recommendations run from #18-27

In GitHub the following instructions were given:

- Please use "Clarification Needed" where you feel like a recommendation lacks clarity
- Please use "Relevance" to comment on the relevance (or lack thereof) for the stakeholder you represent.
- Please use "Implementation Example" to suggest practical implementations or initiatives that are missing for this recommendation.
- It is also possible to submit problems encountered, suggestions, questions, recommendation proposals etc. as issues -> "New Issue"

For the purpose of the workshop the recommendations had been clustered in themes according to the following:

Cluster 1: Identifiers (P-Rec. 1 & 2)

Cluster 2: Metadata (P-Rec. 3, 8, 9, 14, 15, 16, 17)

Cluster 3: Repository (P-Rec. 4, 5, 6, 7)

Cluster 4: Semantic alignment (P-Rec. 10, 11, 12, 13)

Cluster 5: Best practices (BP-Rec. 1-10)

The agenda for the work was the following:

13:00-13:15: Introduction

13:15-14:30: Discussion of the recommendation Session 1

14:30-15:00: Break

15:00-16:45: Discussion of the recommendation Session 2

16:45-17:00: Wrap-Up

Preliminary Workshop Results

The output of the workshop has been thoroughly assessed by the task group, and the implications of this analysis will be reflected in the next version of the recommendations, D2.5 2nd set of Recommendations for FAIR Semantics. The github repository is also still open for feedback and comments. Some preliminary observations can be made in this report.

The participants were mostly highly knowledgeable in the field and quite well prepared and familiar with the subject.

There were a lot of open text comments, which have to be analysed carefully, as well as questions about the best practice recommendations and which parties or stakeholders should act upon which recommendation.

Importance of Recommendation

The majority of recommendations were regarded by the respondents as important, with the following specific exceptions:

1. P-Rec 10: There was considerable divergence of opinion on whether a guiding or foundational ontology is required or can be achieved;
2. P-Rec 11: Some divergence of opinion on whether it was needed, is in the scope of FAIR, and what will be required as a defining conceptual model prior to describing logical relations.
3. P-Rec-15: Some disagreement in respect of the need to reference input semantic artefacts.

Clarity of Recommendation Text

The majority of recommendations can be improved in terms of clarity.

Clarity of Implementation Text

The same applies to text describing implementation: providing concrete examples is requested by many respondents.

Implementation and Compliance Responsibility

There are several cases where the respondents considered implementation a joint responsibility of practitioners and repositories. This will require a clear definition of the the shared responsibility in the next iteration of the recommendations to limit confusion.

Compliance Imperative

There were few cases of consensus in respect of the imperative attached to a recommendation - the notable exception is P-Rec 17 (human and machine readability of provenance). During the revision phase, correspondence between the current wording of the recommendation and the consensus response needs to be evaluated, and appropriate modifications made as required.

Imperative vs Importance

The chart below tests the importance associated with a recommendation against the imperative assigned by the respondents: we would expect a generally positive correlation between relative importance and relative support for a strong imperative.

Participants

Community Representation

Experts from the following communities participated (See Appendix C for details):

The respondents show a strong bias towards research (as opposed to infrastructure), and within research, the majority of participants were from information and computer science domains. There were no participants specifically indicating a discipline outside of natural and life sciences.

Organisation and Initiative Representation

Experts from the following organisations, projects or services were present (See Appendix D):

The type of organisations represented at the workshop showed adequate variety, with no one type dominating.

Clustering of Comments and Suggestions

Workshop comments were classified into a three-level hierarchy. The clustering of comments based on this classification is as follows:

Main Aspect	Secondary Aspect	Classes	Number of Comments
Alignment	Community		2
Alignment	GRDI		1
Alignment	Open Access		(0)
Alignment	Open Data		(0)
Alignment	Open Science		(0)
Alignment	Standards		3
Conceptual Model	Central Repository		6
Conceptual Model	Central Repository	API	2
Conceptual Model	Central Repository	Federated Registry	1
Conceptual Model	Metadata and Data	License	1
Conceptual Model	Metadata and Data	Quality and Maturity	1
Conceptual Model	Metadata and Data		20
Conceptual Model	Model		7
Conceptual Model	Model	Model	1
Conceptual Model	Status Quo	Critical Evaluation	1
Conceptual Model	Vocabulary		12
Implementation	APIs		3
Implementation	Best Practice	Advocacy/ Policy	1
Implementation	Best Practice	API	1
Implementation	Best Practice	Ethics	1
Implementation	Best Practice	Incentives	1
Implementation	Best Practice		13
Implementation	Compliance		1
Implementation	Examples		17
Implementation	Ideas and suggestions		8
Implementation	Maturity		2

Implementation	PID		10
Implementation	Repositories		2
Implementation	Responsibility	Clarity	4
Implementation	Responsibility	Shared	1
Implementation	Responsibility		1
Implementation	Versions and Life Cycle		3
Performance	Evaluation		(0)
Performance	Maturity		1
Recommendation	Concept	Methods	1
Recommendation	Concept	Objects/ Vocabulary	1
Recommendation	Concept	Re-Use	1
Recommendation	Concept		7
Recommendation	Imperative		4
Recommendation	Intent		3
Recommendation	Lack of Consensus		(0)
Recommendation	Text	Clarity	18
Recommendation	Text	Grammar	1
Unclassified	Ambiguous Comments		2

Note: (0) denotes considerations raised by report authors, but were not identified during the workshop

The top 5 categories of comments and issues raised were:

1. Definition of metadata and data differences and elements (20)
2. Clarity of Recommendation Text (18)
3. The need for implementation examples (17) and best practices (13)
4. Definition of a vocabulary (based on a conceptual model) (12)
5. Recommendations on implementation of PIDs (10)

Remedies

The comments received during the workshop were grouped into a 2-tier ‘remedy’ classification to determine the optimal improvements to be made to the recommendations. These are summarised below:

We considered a set of generic remedies to address the issues and comments raised by the workshop participants.

The process proposed for addressing the comments and issues is discussed below:

1. Categorise and Prioritise Issues: This was done using the categories described in the previous section.
2. Define Classified Responses (‘Remedies’): Based on the classification of comments and
3. Organise Responses in a Process: this takes account of dependencies between remedies (for example, we need to define a conceptual model before we can define vocabularies and a metadata schema).
4. Organise Responses in a Framework: some remedies require research, analysis, and synthesis work, while others require community engagement or advocacy. Some responses address policy and sustainability issues, while others are operational.

Framework

Level of Response		Typical Outputs	Typical Activity
High Level	Governance and Sustainability	Policies, statements of intent, conference resolutions, business or user requirements, community engagement structures and processes Marketing and advocacy material	Setting policy, guidelines, and intentions based on community requirements, creating fora and mechanisms for interaction. Advocacy.
	Conceptualisation Governance Architecture	Conceptual models, vision, manifestos, roadmaps of solution(s) to serve community requirements	Analysis of high-level requirements and synthesis of alternative solutions
Mid-Level	Systems Architecture and Standards ‘Outer Loop’	Systems architecture and modularisation, minimum viable system definition, standards for integration and interoperability between modules, roles and responsibilities of humans and machines	Solution selection and elaboration, interface descriptions and standards, alignment with existing standards and architectures
	Systems, Procedures, and Specifications	Definition of standard operating procedures, best practices, and specifications for implementation of individual systems and instances	Design of systems to suit a particular context, adoption and implementation or configuration of standard procedures
	Benchmarking, Compliance, and Maturity	Tests for compliance, definition of maturity of compliance, referrals to reference implementations	Test and compliance monitoring development Publication of benchmarking and test results
Detailed, Operational	Systems development ‘Inner Loop’	Version and configuration-controlled code, vocabularies, ontologies, and services	Systems development Content development Community involvement in iterative refinement
	Systems Use and	Workshops, fora, discussion groups, training	Webinars, conference participation, ...

	Application	events, documentation, user guides, ...	
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Impact of Remedies

The graph below depicts the number of comments and issues that will be addressed by a specific remedy. This can be used to prioritise order in which individual remedies are pursued, cognisant of the framework constraints that may apply.

Planning of Remedy Implementation

1. **Simple Tasks:** These can be addressed quickly and in the very short term (by end November 2020)

Group	Remedy	Specific Task(s) or Elements	Importance
Architecture	Requirements and Considerations	Applicable Standards	2
Architecture	Requirements and Considerations	Content Negotiation	1
Architecture	Requirements and Considerations	Repositories	2
Architecture	Requirements and Considerations	Use Cases	2

Architecture	Standards Definition	Licenses	3
Architecture	Standards Definition	Unique, Persistent Identifiers	2
Implementation	Best Practices	Unique, Persistent Identifiers	15
Revision	Recommendations	Misalignment	5
Revision	Recommendations	Text Clarity	6

2. Less Simple Tasks: Requiring largely research, analysis, and synthesis tasks that can be done without significant additional community engagement. Aim: End December 2020.

Group	Remedy	Specific Task(s) or Elements	Importance
Architecture	Roadmap	Vision and Future Development	2
Architecture	Services Architecture	Specifications and Standards	1
Architecture	Standards Definition	(Stratified) Metadata Schema	7
Architecture	Standards Definition	API Specification	2
Architecture	Standards Definition	Discoverability	2
Architecture	Standards Definition	Extensibility (of semantic coverage in metadata)	2
Architecture	Standards Definition	Metadata Standards and Best Practice	4
Architecture	Standards Definition	Provenance	2
Architecture	Standards Definition	Repository Metadata	1
Architecture	Standards Harmonisation and Re-Use	FsF Work Package liaison in progress	1
Architecture	Standards Landscape Review	Critical Assessment	1
Architecture	Standards Landscape Review	Semantic Web Standards and Technologies	1
Implementation	Best Practices	Suggested Standard Operating Procedures, Policy Suggestions	1
Implementation	Best Practices	(Stratified) Metadata Schema	3
Implementation	Best Practices	Licenses	2
Implementation	Best Practices	Mappings and Crosswalks	1
Implementation	Best Practices	Provenance	1

3. Complex Tasks: Requiring significant effort, and/ or community engagement and consensus, and/ or longer term solutions. Planning is to attain some progress by end February 2021, with some community engagement tasks deferred to a longer-term time frame.

Group	Remedy	Specific Task(s) or Elements	Importance
Architecture	Standards Definition	Conceptual Model and Vocabularies	43
Compliance	Document Best Practices and SOPs	Metadata QA	1
Governance and Sustainability	Advocacy	Sustainable Funding TRUST for Semantic Artefacts	4
Governance and Sustainability	Advocacy	Sustainable Funding TRUST for Semantic Artefacts	4
Governance and Sustainability	Advocacy	TRUST for Semantic Artefacts	2
Governance and Sustainability	Capacity Building	Development of Course Materials	1
Governance and Sustainability	Governance Framework	Consensus Process	7
Governance and Sustainability	Governance Framework	Feedback	1
Implementation	Best Practices	Compliance Measurement	2
Implementation	Best Practices	Examples and Reference Implementations	20
Implementation	Best Practices	Maturity Model	2
Infrastructure	Backbone	Implement compliant repository(ies)	1
Infrastructure	Basic Infrastructure	European Registry/ Repository	1
Infrastructure	Federation	Encourage Adoption	1

Appendix A - Recommendations and their clustering

Preliminary Recommendations			
Rec. #	Recommendation	FAIR Principles	Topic
P-Rec. 1	Use Globally Unique, Persistent and Resolvable Identifier for Semantic Artefacts, their content and their versions	F1	Identifiers
P-Rec. 2	Use Globally Unique, Persistent and Resolvable Identifier for Semantic Artefact Metadata Record	F1, F3	Identifiers
P-Rec. 3	Use a common minimum metadata schema to describe semantic artefacts and their content	F2, R1.1, R1.2 and R1.3	Metadata
P-Rec. 4	Publish the Semantic Artefact and its content in a semantic repository	F4	Repository
P-Rec.5	Semantic repositories should offer a common API to access Semantic Artefacts and their content in various serializations for both use/reuse and indexation by search engines	F4, A1, A1.1	Repository
P- Rec. 6	Build semantic artefacts' search engines that operate across different semantic repositories	F4	Repository
P-Rec. 7	Repositories should offer a secure protocol and user access control functionalities	A1.2	Repository
P-Rec. 8	Define human and machine-readable persistency policies for metadata	A2	Metadata
P-Rec. 9	Semantic artefacts should be compliant with Semantic Web and Linked Data standards	I1	Metadata
P-Rec. 10	Use a Foundational Ontology to align semantic artefacts	I1, I2, I3	Semantic alignment
P-Rec. 11	Use a standardized description for complex logical relations	I1	Semantic alignment
P-Rec. 12	Semantic mappings should use machine-readable formats based on W3C standards	I1, I3, R1.3	Semantic alignment
P-Rec. 13	Crosswalks, mappings and bridging between semantic artefacts should be documented, published and curated	R1.2, R1.3	Semantic alignment
P-Rec. 14	P-Rec. 14: Use standard vocabularies to describe semantic artefacts #14	I2	Metadata

P-Rec. 15	P-Rec. 15: Make the references to the reused third-party semantic artefacts explicit #15	I3, R1.2	Metadata
P-Rec. 16	P-Rec. 16: The semantic artefact should be clearly licenced for machines and humans #16	R1.1	Metadata
P-Rec. 17	P-Rec. 17: Provenance should be clear for both humans and machines #17	R1.2	Metadata
Best Practices Recommendations			
BP-Rec. 1	Use a unique naming convention for concept/class and relations		
BP-Rec. 2	Use an Ontology Naming Convention		
BP-Rec. 3	Use defined ontology design patterns		
BP-Rec. 4	Create mappings validated by domain experts		
BP-Rec. 5	Define workflows between different formats		
BP-Rec. 6	Harmonize the methodologies used to develop semantic artefacts		
BP-Rec. 7	Interact with the designated community and manage user-centric development		
BP-Rec. 8	Provide a structured definition for each concept		
BP-Rec. 9	The underlying logic of semantic artefacts should be accurately grounded on the domain it intends to describe		
BP-Rec. 10	Define a set of governance policies for the semantic artefacts		

Appendix B: Detailed Poll Results

Recommendation 1

Summary of Comments

- Concepts:
 - Vocabulary - clarify meaning of 'artefacts'.
- Improvement to Recommendation Text:
 - Clarify 'content' and what it means in practice.
 - Define the granularity of 'content'.
- Implementation:
 - Spend time on interpreting past and current practices in respect of PIDs
 - Make sure the diversity of supported PIDs is minimised
 - Align with Semantic Web
 - Define and consider guidelines for versioning and life cycle
 - DOIs require conventions in respect of landing pages
 - Provide concrete examples of implementation
- Caveats and Concerns:
 - Governance and a registry of PIDs
 - Versioning and life cycle, dependencies should be managed properly

Recommendation 2

Summary of Comments

- **Concepts:**
 - The need to be precise in respect of definition of metadata and data, the differences if any, and recognition that the data and metadata is often managed in the same digital object
 - Need for an agreed vocabulary (in essence a conceptual model) to define terms in use.
- **Improvement to Recommendation Text:**
 - Important to add "published separately" (i.r.o. data and metadata) to the short form of the recommendation.
- **Implementation:**
 - Clarity in respect of definitions of e.g. 'practitioner'
- **Caveats and Concerns:**
 - Current practices are not necessarily equal to best practices. Critical evaluation required.

Recommendation 3

Summary of Comments

- **Concept:**
 - Quality and maturity of metadata is not uniform, and this has to be accommodated
 - Metadata - do not reinvent the wheel, use existing schema if possible
 - Conceptual model, vocabulary needed for metadata
 - Metadata depends on purpose¹
 - Differentiate ontologies and RDF vocabularies
- **Improvement to Recommendation Text:**
 - Definition of community and concepts such as 'practitioner'.
- **Implementation:**
 - Many more examples required for different use cases and situations
- **Caveats and Concerns:**
 - Alignment with community and existing standards, FDO vocabularies
 - Harmonize with other FAIR object practices
- **Ideas and Suggestions:**
 - Use RDA for endorsement

¹ Work is underway to define this - see [concept](#).

Recommendation 4

Summary of Comments

- **Concept:**
 - Recommendations required for persistent repositories to use
 - How does one find a repository?
 - Protocols for semantic repositories
- **Implementation:**
 - Definitions and examples of persistent repositories
 - Role of PIDs and GUPRI to be defined
 - PID and a git repository should be adequate
- **Ideas and Suggestions:**
 - Mirroring requirements for persistent identification and repositories
 - GUPRI means a repository is not required

Recommendation 5

Summary of Comments

- **Concept:**
 - A common API (schema, protocols, ...) will be required
 - Indexing must be possible via API
- **Implementation:**
 - Best practices should include guidance on repository ethics, protocols, indexability
- **Caveats and Concerns:**
 - Use FAIR standards such as SmartAPI
- **Ideas and Suggestions:**
 - Verify compliance with recommendations and best practices

Recommendation 6

Summary of Comments

- **Concept:**
 - Important to support multiple repositories that meet requirements
- **Implementation:**
 - Consider using major search engines (Google) for indexing
 - Liaise with specialists to determine requirements and implement
 - Machine readability will be a prerequisite for this recommendation

Recommendation 7

Summary of Comments

- **Concept:**
 - Repository metadata is also important
- **Improvement to Recommendation Text:**
 - None
- **Implementation:**
 - Consider European-wide support for repositories
 - Secure protocols are important but open access should also be available
- **Caveats and Concerns:**
 - Cannot exclude open access protocols
- **Ideas and Suggestions:**
 - Resourcing will determine in practice what can be achieved

Recommendation 8

Summary of Comments

- **Concept:**
 - Provenance and versioning graphs should be part of the minimum metadata schema.
- **Improvement to Recommendation Text:**
 - Recommendation is not clear at first reading
- **Implementation:**
 - Examples needed!
- **Caveats and Concerns:**
 - Policy is a statement of intent and will be different from one organisation to another
- **Ideas and Suggestions:**
 - Use Nanopublications for this

Recommendation 9

Summary of Comments

- **Concept:**
 - Make a clear distinction between standards and other formalisms
 - Potentially merge or at least align with P11.
 - Compliance with minimum set of standards will be more realistic
- **Improvement to Recommendation Text:**
 - Distinguish between serializations and languages
 - PDF version is more acceptable
- **Implementation:**
 - Examples - especially success stories published as examples.
- **Caveats and Concerns:**
 - Not aligned with P11.

Recommendation 10

- **Concept:**
 - Foundational ontology (conceptual model) is possibly required.
 - One should clarify to which type of semantic artefact this recommendation applies. Probably vocabularies, taxonomies, etc., would not benefit much but it may be relevant to proper ontologies aiming at supporting inference.
- **Improvement to Recommendation Text:**
 - Consider time-stamping recommendations: now, medium term, long term.
- **Implementation:**
 - Examples needed.
- **Caveats and Concerns:**
 - Achieving a foundational ontology will be complex or maybe impossible.
- **Ideas and Suggestions:**

This recommendation deals with quality, not FAIRness - remove.

Recommendation 11

Summary of Comments

- **Concept:**
 - A higher-order conceptual model describing objects and relations will be required
 - At a minimum described in OWL
- **Caveats and Concerns:**
 - Concerns are expressed that this is not a requirement for FAIR.

Recommendation 12

Summary of Comments

- Concepts:
 - Not really a FAIR requirement.
- Improvement to Recommendation Text:
 - 'W3C' as a standard is too wide and ambiguous - need to define standards more specifically.

Recommendation 13

Summary of Comments

- **Concepts:**
 - Documentation requirements must be part of metadata of some type
 - Humans need standard vocabularies more than machines
 - A model for mappings required, as well as persistence and vocabularies
 - Maps between data and metadata are different from those between metadata
- **Improvement to Recommendation Text:**
 - Distinction needed between internal and external mappings
- **Implementation:**
 - Detection of poor alignment between artefacts
 - Provenance of mappings to be documented and available
 - Examples needed
- **Caveats and Concerns:**
 - Curation of mappings in the long term could prove difficult
 - Recommendation is good, but implementation is better

Recommendation 14

Summary of Comments

- **Concept:**
 - Flexibility will be required in terms of metadata vocabulary guidelines and imperatives
 - Additional descriptors will be needed in addition to standard vocabularies
 - Make maximum use of existing vocabularies
 - Enumerate vocabularies to be used
- **Ideas and Suggestions:**
 - Consider merging with P-Rec #3.
 -

Recommendation 15

Summary of Comments

- **Concept:**
 - Differentiate between ontologies and SKOS vocabularies
 - Clarify the type of re-use (full import, URI cherry picking, or URI reuse only)
- **Improvement to Recommendation Text:**
 - Is unique identification and persistent identification the same thing? If not, clarify the difference in conceptual model
- **Implementation:**
 - Best practices should indicate preferred referencing behaviour

Recommendation 16

Summary of Comments

- **Implementation:**
 - Nuance when parts of an ontology uses third-party semantic artefacts and the licenses are not the same: what is the resulting license? Partly addressed by the 'legal interoperability' work in RDA.
- **Caveats and Concerns:**
 - Make sure machine-readable licenses are available.

Recommendation 17

Summary of Comments

- **Concept:**
 - It could be difficult to standardise private licenses
- **Improvement to Recommendation Text:**
 - Define provenance properly
- **Implementation:**
 - Either explicitly says that we need to use PROV or precisely what is meant by "provenance"
- **Caveats and Concerns:**
 - Provenance for an artefact and for elements of the artefact are not always the same.

Appendix C

Environmental science

Geoscience

Ecological data

Oceanography

Marine Community

Life sciences

High pathogenic Agents

Photon community

Neutron community

Qualitative researcher

Researcher

Indigenous data

Computer Science

Data Science

Software Development

Data architect

Software engineering

Ontology engineering

Large facilities

Repository infrastructure

Research data portal

Controlled vocabularies

Information sciences

Semantic Interoperability

Lexical resources

Terminology provider

Thesaurus governance
Ontology Repository
Ontology
Ontology development
Metadata
Metadata standards

Research Data Management
FAIR principles
FAIR roadmap plan
Decision Support
Funders
Health research funder

Appendix D

AgroPortal
BioPortal
CODATA
FAIRSF AIR
DARIAH ERIC
DANS KNAW
ISKO Low Countries
DOI Service
ICOS
ENVRI FAIR
GO FAIR
eLTER
EOSC FAIR WG
ERINHA AISBL
FAIRsFAIR
RDA
EOSC Life
ERINHA Advance
ExPaNDS
FAIRplus EBI
FSRTG
Helmholtz Metadata Collab
Helmholtz Association
Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin
INRAE FooSIN
NVS BODC-NOC
SeaDataNet
Uni Politécnica Madrid, Ontology Engineering Group
RDA VSSIG
University
University library
US Geological Survey
VODAN

